

**GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN KARNATAKA:
AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS**

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Abstract

The role of higher education in Karnataka is multifaceted and crucial to the state's social, economic, technological, and cultural development. Karnataka is one of the leading states in India in terms of educational infrastructure, particularly in higher education, and this has significantly contributed to its growth in many areas. However, higher education is the crucial to national development and it has come to be recognized as the key tools of socio-economic development in the weaker sections of the people in rural and urban areas. It plays an important role in community for providing the skill development and thereby social development because the higher education develops the skill, abilities, and attitude and encourage for social development. It is a powerful instrument of increasing access to highly skilled and high paid employments and by providing this employment it helps in achieving social development. The performance of higher education in ensuring overall growth and development is very essential. This paper has deliberated present growth and development of higher education and the trend in enrolment in Indian higher education in India as well as Karnataka state.

Keywords: Higher Education, Colleges, Enrollment, and Institutions.

Introduction

Higher education is one of the important constituents of human development and recognized as fundamental human rights. It plays sustains economic growth by providing high knowledgeable skills, awareness of globalization, valuable of human beings, more of employment opportunities, self-reliance, decision making and need full of future living. The future belongs to India the largest vibrant democratic system in the world, teeming with opportunities. It is a very an important role of human development in the country. It is for short and long-term economic growth and development of human resource which can take responsibility for social, economic and scientific development of the country. It not only provides skills and qualification to new generation but also creates in their minds the awareness of environmental and social realities and therefore helps in attaining for them a better standard of living. It is the substance which helps the economy to grow and stabilize the resources for the improvement of the society. India possesses a highly developed higher education system which offers facility of education and training in almost all aspects of human creative, employment generation and intellectual endeavors: arts and humanities; natural, mathematical and social sciences, engineering; medicine, dentistry; agriculture; education; law; commerce and management; music and performing arts; national and foreign languages; culture; communications etc.

The Indian Higher Education system, which includes Technical Education, is one of the largest of the world, just after the United States and China. Higher Education is the most powerful tools to build a knowledge-based society for the future. It is providing people with an opportunity to reflect on the critical social, economic, cultural, moral and spiritual issues facing humanity. It is contributing to national development through dissemination of specialized knowledge, awareness of decision making, empowerment of

women and skills. Being at the apex of the educational pyramid, it plays a key role in producing quality teachers for the country's education.

Objective of the Study

1. To examine the patterns and status of growth in higher education across India over a defined period.
2. To evaluate the regional trends and growth in higher education specifically within the state of Karnataka.

Materials and Methods

The research article is mainly based on secondary data. The secondary data for the information has been collected with the help of Report on Higher Education in India: Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012–2017) and beyond and ASHE- Annual Status of Higher Education, Books, Magazines, Newspapers, Research Articles, Research Journals, E-Journals, 2015. The research paper was carried out by statistical tools like annual growth rate and compound annual growth rate.

Growth of Higher Education Institutions in India

Higher education is an unimaginable advancement in the field of knowledge and social and national aspirations of the people all over the India. It is the responsibility of education to encourage the all-round development of an individual's personality, thus help urban-rural areas become an active member of a knowledge society and a productive citizen of this country. The Indian higher education system is one of the largest in the world in terms of the number of colleges and universities. From 350 universities and 16,982 colleges in 2005-06, the numbers have gone up to 799 universities, 39,071 colleges,

and 11,923 diploma-level institutions in 2015-16. There is need to match the supply with demand and to dovetail education policy to employment opportunities.

Therefore, higher education needs to be futuristic and envision areas that will generate future employment opportunities, save the environmental resources, developing for human development resources and accordingly offer suitable courses for students. The gross enrolment ratio (GER) in higher education in India has improved to 23.6 per cent in 2014-15 from to 21.5 per cent in 2012-13 with 14.3 million students enrolled in 2005-06 as compared to total enrolment in higher education has been estimated to be 34.2 million in 2014-15 with 18.5 million boys and 15.7 million girls. Girls constitute 45.5 per cent of the total enrolment.

**Table-1 Growth and Trends in Higher Education Institutions in India
(2011-12 to 2015-16)**

Year	Number of Institutions			Annual Growth Rate (%)		
	Universities/ University level Institutions	Colleges	Total Higher Education Institutions	Universities/ University level Institutions	Colleges	Total Higher Education Institutions
2004-05	348	17625	17973	--	--	--
2005-06	378	18064	18442	7.94	2.43	2.54
2006-07	419	19370	19739	9.79	6.74	6.57
2007-08	461	20677	21138	9.11	6.32	6.62
2008-09	471	22064	22535	2.12	6.29	6.20
2009-10	504	25951	26455	6.55	14.98	14.82
2010-11	544	31324	31868	7.35	17.15	16.99
2011-12	642	34852	35494	15.26	10.12	10.22
2012-13	667	35525	36192	3.75	1.89	1.93
2013-14	723	36634	37357	7.75	3.03	3.12
2014-15	760	38498	39258	4.87	4.84	4.84
2015-16	799	39071	39870	4.88	1.47	1.53

Source: Government of India (2016), Ministry of Human Resource Development, Department of Higher Education, All India Survey on Higher Education (2015-16), New Delhi.

The trends and growth rates of higher education institutions in India since 2004-05, are given in table-1. The number of Universities in the country has registered an increase from 348 in 2004-05 to and 799 in 2015-16, which denotes more than a tenfold increase. During the same period, the number of colleges has gone up from 17,625 to 39,071. The computed annual average compounded growth rate of higher education institutions reveals that there was a phenomenal growth during the 2005-06 (2.54%) and in 2006-07 (6.57%) and the total growth rate came down to an all-time low of 1.53% during the 2015-16. Therefore, number of institutions positive impact of higher education institutions in India.

Table-2 Enrollment in Higher Education in India (2011-12 to 2015-16)

Year	Male	Female
2011-12	16173473	13010858
2012-13	16617294	13535123
2013-14	17495394	14840840
2014-15	18488619	15723018
2015-16	18594723	15990058

Source: Government of India, Education Statistics 2015-16.

**Graph-1 Enrollment in Higher Education in India
(Period: 2011-12 to 2015-16)**

Trends of Higher Education Institutions in Karnataka

Trends of higher education have been a concurrent responsibility of the central and state governments. Accordingly, growth and trends of Universities and Colleges in Karnataka has been influenced by the policies of the University Grants Commission as well as that of the Government of Karnataka. Government of Karnataka deals with all issues related to general higher education through the Directorate of Collegiate Education which functions under the guidance of the Department of Higher and Technical Education.

The Department of Collegiate Education was set up in the year 1960, and has since been striving to make quality higher education affordable and accessible to all sections of students. The Department of Collegiate Education oversees the administration of 411 Government First Grade Colleges and 321 Private aided colleges affiliated to 14 state universities, through its 6 regional offices located at Bengaluru, Mysuru, Mangaluru, Shivamogga, Dharwad and Kalaburagi.

Status of Institutions and Enrollment in Karnataka

The institutions and enrollment are one of the important characters of government colleges and the average strength in government and aided degree colleges. The average strength in government and aided degree colleges is 738.59 and 700.42 respectively (Vide in Table-3).

Table-3 Status of Institutions in Karnataka 2015-16

Managements	Government	Private Aided	Total
Institutions	411	321	732
Students	3,03,556	2,24,835	5,28,394
Average Per College (Nos)	738.59	700.42	721.85

Source: Economic Survey of Karnataka 2015-16, GOK

Table-5 Growth of Enrollment in Degree colleges in Karnataka (Period: 2007-08 to 2015-16)

Year	Boys	AGR	Girls	AGR	Total	Total AGR	M:F Ratios
2007-08	174729	--	15458 4	--	32931 3	--	53:47
2008-09	179380	2.59	16373 1	5.59	34311 1	4.02	52:48
2009-10	181779	1.32	17622 6	7.09	35797 5	4.15	51:49
2010-11	181018	-0.42	18679 0	5.66	36760 5	2.62	49:51
2011-12	226785	20.18	23531 3	20.62	45709 7	19.58	49:51
2012-13	229681	1.26	23547 1	0.07	46515 2	1.73	49:51
2013-14	247140	7.06	28286 7	16.76	53000 7	12.24	47:53
2014-15	251078	1.57	28398 6	0.39	53506 4	0.95	47:53
2015-16	234655	-7.00	29373 9	3.32	52839 4	-1.26	44:56

Source: Government of Karnataka (2017), Economic Survey of Karnataka 2017-18.

Table-4 shows that enrolments for degree courses have not registered a steady increasing trend in the State. In fact, negative growth has been observed in the growth of overall enrolments during 2015-16. Further, in case of boys, during the same period there is negative growth rate of (-) 6.54. The male-female ratio which was in favour of boys during 2007-08 to 2009- 10 has got reversed during 2010-11. This same trend has continued and according to 2015-16 enrolments the ratio is 44:56 and this is not a case of improvement in gender parity.

Conclusion

Higher education is one of the plays in human being and economy all the over all world and country as well as state. It plays is an important component in the progress of any development nations. The entire culture of higher education should promote freedom of thought in spiritual knowledge and thinking. It should foster the ethos of freedom of worship and gratefulness. The diversity in higher education institutions is an indication of many levels of challenges that we face while dealing with the system of higher education. No, one segment of this entire system resembles the other in its functioning. Consequently, the challenges in relation to governance and reform of these institutions are equally multifaceted.

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